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INTERPLAY OF SUPERVISOR SUPPORT, TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP, JOB SATISFACTION, WORK ENGAGEMENT, AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN REMOTE WORK SETTINGS: EXPLORATION THROUGH STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELING

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Abstract

Remote work is increasingly becoming a permanent feature of organizational design, especially in developing countries like Pakistan. Therefore, there is a need to understand how leadership contributes to such working models to create desired employee outcomes. This research explores how transformational leadership (TL) influences job satisfaction, work engagement, and employee performance in remote settings, taking perceived supervisor support as a potential mediator. This quantitative cross-sectional study used the lens of Transformational Leadership Theory. The study collected responses from 321 IT professionals who were working in remote settings. Data was collected through standardized scales. Covariance-based Structural Equation Modeling was used to examine the relationships among study constructs. Findings have shown that employees who worked with a transformational leader experienced a higher level of job satisfaction, greater engagement at work, and enhanced performance. It was also found that perceived supervisor support partially plays a mediating role, emphasizing its importance in translating leadership into positive employee outcomes. This study tries to extend the existing models of leadership in remote settings and provides actionable recommendations that organizations can use to promote both employee engagement and enhanced job performance. It makes clear that having people supporting each other works better in virtual settings. The results respond quickly to the shifts happening in today's digital workplace.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership, Perceived Supervisor Support, Employee Performance, Remote Settings, Digital Era, SEM

Introduction

The global shift to telecommuting due to technological advances and the COVID-19 pandemic has dramatically altered the mode of operation in organizations. Although telecommuting opportunities provide flexibility and productivity, they also have negative effects, such as isolation of employees, communication challenges, reduced cohesion, and digital exhaustion (Franken et al., 2020; Hodder, 2020; Wang et al., 2021). These negativities indicate and create the need for leadership, which is required to sustain employee satisfaction, engagement, and productivity in virtual workplaces (Kniffin et al., 2021).

Transformational leadership (TL) has become one of the most powerful leadership styles in ambiguous and dynamic situations. TL enhances individual and organizational performance by idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individual consideration of workers, making them feel inspired and energized to do better than expected (Avolio & Yammarino, 2013; Bass & Riggio, 2006). Past studies demonstrate that TL fosters work engagement, job satisfaction, and improved performance in traditional workplaces (Eldor & Harpaz, 2016; Purvanova & Bono, 2009). However, the role of TL in virtual offices, in which face-to-face interaction does not matter, and executives must rely on technology, has not been studied to the limit (Bartsch et al., 2021; Contreras et al., 2020).

Another but distinct element in the virtual environment is perceived supervisor support (PSS) that encompasses the feelings that employees hold about their supervisors being supportive of their work and that they care about them (Eisenberger et al., 2016; Kurtessis et al., 2017). It helps in decreasing isolation and stress and increasing trust, commitment, and performance in virtual workplaces where employees are not physically

present due to geographical separation (Charoensukmongkol & Phungsoonthorn, 2021; Gajendran & Joshi, 2012). Teleworkers require supervisor responsiveness, recognition, and empathy to achieve job satisfaction and participation (Alexander et al., 2021). Nevertheless, owing to its significance, very little research has been done exploring PSS as a mediator between TL and employee outcomes in virtual working environments.

Employee performance, like job satisfaction, work engagement, and performance are critical organizational health indicator. Job satisfaction indicates favorable employee attitudes about their job and strongly correlates with retention and motivation (Amiruddin & Yudiarso, 2023). Work engagement, as vigor, dedication, and absorption, predicts productivity and organizational commitment (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018). Employee performance in both task and contextual aspects determines long-term competitiveness (Andrade et al., 2020). Even though TL is highly associated with these consequences in traditional work environments, the circumstances of remote work necessitate further examination since autonomy, reliance on technology, and decreased physical oversight reconfigure these associations.

Leadership and supervisory help are also a perception of cultural context. In collectivist cultures, like Pakistan, personal relationships and respect for the hierarchy are at the center stage in influencing employee perceptions (Hofstede, 2001; Iqbal et al., 2015). As the IT industry of Pakistan is quickly switching to remote and hybrid operations after the pandemic (Haroon & Zeeshan, 2023). The question of how TL and PSS influence employee performance in this context should be answered. Although increasing use of remote work is being experienced in Pakistan, empirical information on the interaction between TL, PSS, and employee performance in the context of remote work has not been thoroughly studied, and PSS is tested in the research as a mediator. This study tries to explore these aspects. Since remote work is still developing, the mechanisms of how leadership and supervisory support contribute to positive outcomes will still be of importance to organizational resilience and the well-being of employees.

Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

Transformational Leadership and Employee Outcomes

Transformational leadership (TL) is a highly studied type of leadership that influences followers to perform better than expected through idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration (Bass & Riggio, 2006; McCleskey, 2014). TL fosters trust, motivation, and commitment through the association between personal purpose and organizational vision (Avolio & Yammarino, 2013). Past research demonstrates that TL is positively correlated with significant employee outcomes, such as job satisfaction, engagement, and performance (Judge & Piccolo, 2004; Purvanova & Bono, 2009). Transformational leaders play an even bigger role in remote work settings because the digital worlds exacerbate the isolation and the risks of disengagement (Bartsch et al., 2021; Contreras et al., 2020). Based on this literature, the following set of hypotheses can be proposed;

H_1 = Transformational leadership positively impacts job satisfaction in remote work settings.

H_2 = Transformational leadership positively impacts work engagement in remote work settings.

H_3 = Transformational leadership positively impacts employee performance in remote work settings.

Transformational Leadership and Perceived Supervisor Support

Perceived supervisor support (PSS) describes the perceptions of the workers that their supervisors value their effort and care about their well-being (Eisenberger et al., 2016; Kurtessis et al., 2017). Supervisory support perceptions are likely to improve with the help of inspirational communication and individual consideration by transformational leaders (Breevaart et al., 2014). In disbursed environments, where people do not have enough time to interact with each other in everyday situations, responsiveness, recognition, and empathy are leadership behaviors that are crucial to developing PSS (Sinclair et al., 2021). Here is the proposed path;

H_4 = Transformational leadership positively impacts perceived supervisor support in remote work settings.

Perceived Supervisor support and Employee outcomes

There is substantial evidence that PSS is associated with job satisfaction, engagement, and performance. When supervisors reward, coach, and communicate with the employees, they become loyal, devoted, and motivated (Kossek et al., 2018; Rahim et al., 2020). PSS can be used to reduce stress, burnout, and turnover, and enhance engagement and productivity in remote working environments (Charoensukmongkol & Phungsoonthorn, 2021). Such cultures as Pakistan that support collectivism and where subordinates require interpersonal care and respect are likely to appreciate supervisory support (Iqbal et al., 2015). The following set of hypotheses can be proposed here

H_5 = Perceived supervisor support positively impacts job satisfaction in remote work settings

H_6 = Perceived supervisor support positively impacts work engagement in remote work settings.

H_7 = Perceived supervisor support positively impacts employee performance in remote work settings.

Mediating Role of Perceived Supervisor Support

PSS is recognized to play a mediating role between leadership and employee outcomes that is becoming more common in organizational behavior research. Transformational leaders also manipulate the sense of support among the employees, which subsequently translate into satisfaction, engagement, and increased performance (Penger & Černe, 2014). PSS is especially a psychological factor connecting the behavior of the leaders and the outcomes of the employees in remote work, where employees are largely reliant on the virtual mode of communication (Boccoli et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2021). Here are the proposed mediating paths

H_8 = Perceived supervisor support mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction in remote work settings.

H_9 = Perceived supervisor support mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and work engagement in remote work settings.

H_{10} = Perceived supervisor support mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance in remote work settings.

In Remote Work Settings.

Methods

The positivist paradigm was followed in this study. A cross-sectional survey design with quantitative approach was adopted to examine the interplay of transformational leadership, perceived supervisor support, job satisfaction, work engagement and employee performance. The cross-sectional study was used to capture the perceptions of employees on persistent remote working at a given time. This design was also effective in terms of data collection and testing hypothesized relationships.

The target population was the professionals of the information technology (IT) sector in Pakistan; a sector that underwent a dramatic switch to remote work after the COVID-19 pandemic. The IT professionals were chosen due to the fact that their job is highly digitalized, which made them reflective of the dynamics in the remote working setting. Five hundred questionnaires were distributed electronically using professional networks and contacts at the company. Out of them, 321 valid responses were returned and gave a response rate of 64.2%. The sample size was chosen considering the minimum requirement of the main statistical technique, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). This sample size can provide sufficient statistical power to test the proposed model and specified paths.

This study followed purposive sampling (a type of non-probability sampling) due to the lack of a sampling frame for such a dynamic population and information about the total size of the population. The online data collection was done via email and professional social networks e.g. LinkedIn. The survey was conducted on a voluntary basis, and the respondents were guaranteed anonymity as well as confidentiality. Further, prior to the completion of the survey, informed consent was also taken. Anonymity was encouraged to reduce common method bias, and the survey questions were not randomised to curb the tendency to respond in a pattern. A well-structured questionnaire was used to collect the data. The constructs of the study were standardized to address the validity and reliability concerns in the study. Transformational Leadership is evaluated using a scale introduced by Carless et al. (2000). Perceived Supervisor Support Measured using items that were created by Rhoades et al. (2001) and assess employee perceptions that their supervisors value their work and care about their well-being. The Job Satisfaction Scale was evaluated with standard items of Talukder et al. (2018) which is a measure of the affective response of employees to the jobs. Work Engagement is measured using the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES) by Schaufeli and Bakker

(2004) which includes the vigor, dedication, and absorption. Employee Performance is based on the performance of employees, and the measurement and assessment scale is founded on Andrade et al. (2020) which is based on task and contextual performance. Data on demographic variables (age, gender, education, and experience) were also collected to characterize the sample.

SmartPLS 4.0 was used to perform Covariance-based structure equation model (CB-SEM). This type of SEM model is considered more robust than partial least square-based structure equation modeling (PLS-SEM). The demographic factors and the key study variables were summarized using descriptive statistics. The common method bias (CMB) was also tested using the single-factor test by Harman, which revealed that common method bias was not a serious problem. To ensure the reliability and validity of the measurement model, various tests were performed, such as Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability (CR), factor loadings, and average variance extracted (AVE). The structural model was then used to determine and test the validity of the direct and mediating relationships between constructs. The regression coefficients were estimated in a structural model, and their hypothesis testing was done through bootstrapped-based standard errors.

The research was conducted with a high level of ethical principles. The participation was voluntary, and informed consent forms on the purpose of the study, procedures, and confidentiality were given to the respondents. No personal identifiable information was gathered. The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the University of Gujrat, Pakistan, where data collection and processing were performed in accordance with institutional and academic ethical procedures.

Results

Description of Sample Characteristics

There were 321 participants who willingly participated in this study. Out of these 66.0% were males and almost 80.0% were having age between 25-30 years. Further, more than 70% participants were graduates and post-graduates with full-time employment status. This distribution aligns with the demographic patterns in the IT sector. Almost all workers in remote positions in IT show attainment of at least graduate-level education, which shows the essential requirement of technical abilities and academic qualifications for such roles.

Table 1 is the reflection of basic descriptive statistics, reliability, and correlation analysis between the main constructs of the study. Five main constructs: transformational leadership (TL), job satisfaction (JS), work engagement (WE), employee performance (EP), and perceived supervisor support (PSS), have been presented in the form of mean and standard deviation. The mean values close to 4.00 indicate that all these constructs have shown higher agreement towards these concepts. Further, the Cronbach alpha of all constructs is more than 0.70, which indicates that all constructs have good levels of internal reliability and trustworthy adopted scales. The correlation analysis indicates that all relationships are statistically significant, even at low level of significance 0.01. All correlations are positive, which displays that higher levels of TL can enhance JS, WE, PSS, and EP.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics & Correlation Analysis

	TL	JS	WE	EP	PSS
Transformational Leadership	1				
Job Satisfaction	.894**	1			
Work Engagement	.920**	.909**	1		
Employee Performance	.916**	.869**	.930**	1	
Perceived Supervisor Support	.809**	.774**	.808**	.830**	1
Mean	3.852	3.781	3.914	3.889	3.873
Standard Deviation	0.675	0.698	0.692	0.674	0.696
Cronbach Alpha	0.904	0.882	0.931	0.941	0.790

Assessment of Measurement Model

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) or measurement model was also developed to ensure the construct validity and reliability of the adopted constructs. For the construct validity, the standardized factor loadings were observed, and all of these were above the suggested level of 0.70. Further, high values of Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) also ensure convergent validity and reliability. Table 2 contains all this information and indicates that all constructs CR and AVE exceeded 0.70 and 0.50, respectively. In CB-SEM, there are various model fit indices (Chi-square/ degree of freedom (CMIN/DF), Comparative fit index (CFI), Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), Standardized root mean square residual (SRMR)), which can gauge the suitability of the measurement model. The measurement model showed an excellent fit (CMIN/DF = 1.377, CFI = 0.977, TLI = 0.975, SRMR = 0.026, RMSEA = 0.034, PClose = 0.136). Because the estimated values of all these fit indices are as required. These findings prove the validity and reliability of the measurement model. The large values of the factor loadings, good model fit and reasonable reliability values indicate that the dataset will be used in further to estimate structural paths and can perform hypothesis tests on how the study variables relate to each other. Lastly, the discriminant validity was also assessed through Fornell-Larcker criteria. In this criterion, inter-construct correlations should be less than the square roots of the AVE of each construct. Table 2 also showed that the square root of AVE of each construct (placed at diagonals) was greater than off-diagonals (inter-correlations). These findings ensured the presence of discriminant validity among these constructs.

Table 2: Assessment of Measurement Model

Validity and Reliability									
	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)	TL	JS	WE	EP	PSS
TL	0.958	0.868	0.846	0.965	0.931				
JS	0.871	0.830	0.826	0.880	.894**	0.911			

WE	0.967	0.890	0.865	0.975	.920**	.909**	0.943	
EP	0.944	0.880	0.865	0.950	.916**	.869**	0.938	
PSS	0.734	0.700	0.689	0.740	.809**	.774**	.808**	0.837

Assessment of Structural Model

After the measurement model, the structural model was estimated and assessed as per the guidelines provided in the literature. This particular model is used to test the hypotheses of the study. Figure 1 is the finalized structural model in which each arrow from one construct to another is the reflection of a hypothesis. The overall fitness of the model was assessed through the same indices that have been used in the measurement model. Table 3 contains all such information and thresholds provided in the literature. It was confirmed that the structural model was an excellent fit to the observed data to the proposed model (CMIN/DF = 1.851, CFI = 0.953, TLI = 0.963, SRMR = 0.041, RMSEA = 0.031, Pclose = 0.128).

Table 3: *Fitness of Structural Model*

Model Fit Measures		
Measures	Threshold	Estimates of Models
CMIN	-	1130.885
DF	-	611
CMIN/DF	Between 1 and 3	1.851
CFI	>0.95	0.953
TLI	> 0.95	0.963
SRMR	<0.08	0.041
RMSEA	<0.08	0.031
Pclose	>0.05	0.128

Table 4 presents the findings related to direct and indirect hypotheses of the study. These findings have used bootstrap-based standard errors to test the hypotheses. Bootstrapping analysis of 5,000 samples was used to determine the significance of proposed paths. This resampling process gives more precise confidence and potentially yields generalizable study findings. Statistical findings have shown that all structural paths are positive and showing positive influence of constructs on each other. Further, these paths are statistically significant at 5% level of significance. TL has a positive impact on the JS, WE, EP, and PSS (b = 0.727, b = 0.356, b = 0.620, b = 0.851), respectively. Similarly, PSS has a slightly weak but significant effect on JS and EP. While the regression coefficient of PSS → WE was showing a substantial impact, with b = 0.851. These findings reflect that the support behavior of leadership boosts both affective and behavioral reactions of the employees, which foster increased satisfaction, motivation, and productivity.

Figure 1: Finalized Structural Model of the Study

The second half of Table 4 indicates that mediating paths were also significant. The mediation analyses also indicated that PSS significantly mediated the relationship between TL and JS, WE, and EP. In particular, mediating paths for JS ($b = 0.168$), WE ($b = 0.494$), and EP ($b = 0.298$) were positive and statistically significant. The significance of these paths indicates that the effects of TL on JS, WE, and EP can be enhanced and transmitted through PSS.

Table 4: Direct and Indirect Path-related Hypotheses Testing

Direct effect	Beta	SE	t-values	95% CI		p-value	Status
				Lower	Upper		
H1: TL → JS	0.727	0.057	12.75	0.615	0.839	0.000	Accepted
H2: TL → WE	0.715	0.073	4.87	0.213	0.499	0.000	Accepted
H3: TL → EP	0.619	0.051	12.16	0.520	0.720	0.000	Accepted
H4: TL → PSS	0.851	0.047	18.11	0.758	0.944	0.000	Accepted

H5: PSS → JS	0.197	0.046	4.28	0.107	0.287	0.000	Accepted
H6: PSS → WE	0.850	0.065	13.08	0.723	0.977	0.000	Accepted
H7: PSS → EP	0.350	0.050	7.00	0.252	0.448	0.000	Accepted

Mediating Effect	Beta	SE	t-values	95% CI		p-value	Status
				Lower	Upper		
H8: TL → PSS → JS	0.168	0.042	4.00	0.086	0.250	0.000	Accepted
H9: TL → PSS → WE	0.494	0.071	6.95	0.362	0.609	0.000	Accepted
H10: TL → PSS → EP	0.298	0.055	5.42	0.190	0.406	0.000	Accepted

Discussion

This research focused on how transformational leadership (TL) affects job satisfaction (JS), work engagement (WE), and employee performance (EP) when working remotely and the mediating impact of perceived supervisor support (PSS). The results furnish great evidence that TL can greatly boost EP and that PSS is a valuable medium via which leadership can have its effects. The proposed theoretical framework is justified in this study by the CB-SEM, which is specifically used here to test this theoretical model.

The findings affirm that TL impacts positively on JS, WE, and EP of remote IT workers in Pakistan. This aligns with the previous research in traditional work environments that emphasized the transformational ability of leaders to inspire, motivate, and align the workforce close to the organizational objectives (Judge & Piccolo, 2004; Purvanova & Bono, 2009). Such behaviors become even more important in the remote context, where leaders will need to replace the lack of face-to-face communication by creating trust and commitment in the digital environment (Bartsch et al., 2021; Contreras et al., 2020). The distance workers seem to appreciate leaders who give them vision, show empathy, as well as challenge their intellects, which supports the concept that TL can still be relevant in various organizational environments.

The research also established that TL is a strong predictor of PSS, which implies that leaders who demonstrate the trait of individualized consideration and responsiveness are viewed as supportive. This is in agreement with the previous studies, which indicate that transformational behaviors improve trust and supervisory relationships (Breevaart et al., 2014). In dispersed settings, where there is little opportunity to allow informal interactions, visible leadership assistance is a critical factor in maintaining feelings of concern and appreciation among the employees. Supervisor support, as perceived, was also found to greatly contribute to JS, engagement and performance. This confirms earlier results that supervisors who are concerned about the well-being of employees promote higher levels of loyalty, commitment, and motivation (Charoensukmongkol & Phungsoonthorn, 2021; Kurtessis et al., 2017). This is increased in the case of collectivist cultures like in Pakistan, where employees are particularly sensitive to interpersonal care and hierarchies (Iqbal et al., 2015). The close association between PSS and WE indicates

that the supportive behaviors are known to keep the employees committed and revitalized despite the adversity of remote work, such as digital fatigue and isolation. On the same note, the positive correlation with performance shows that support motivates employees not only to do what he or she is supposed to do but also to go the extra mile.

Notably, the findings supported the fact that PSS mediates the relationship between TL and employee outcomes like EP and WE. This observation contributes to leadership theory since it reveals that TL influence is not direct only but also indirect as well, acting in the perceptions of support that are built by the supervisory behavior. This observation adds to the body of evidence highlighting the significance of psychological processes that turn leadership styles into real-life effects (Penger & Černe, 2014). This mechanism is especially salient in the environment of remote work, where employees are more inclined to depend on the intentional work of the supervisors to deliver recognition, feedback, and empathy.

On a theoretical note, the study contributes to three aspects. First, it applies the theory of transformational leadership to the digital or remote work setting and proves that it remains relevant even in an environment where the lack of physical distance may otherwise undermine the leader-follower relationships. Second, it brings to the fore the concept of PSS as a key mediator, contributing to the research on how transformational leadership is translated into favourable employee outcomes. Third, targeting the Pakistani IT industry, the study expands the cross-cultural literature on leadership and offers an understanding of the leadership process in a collectivist and fast-paced digitalizing economy.

The results also have practical implications for the organizations and managers. Companies, depending on the remote or hybrid work patterns, ought to invest in leadership development initiatives that focus on the transformational behaviors which involve vision communication, personalized support, and intellectual stimulation. Supervisors also need to be trained to be regular recognizers, regular feedback providers, responsive, and empathetic via the virtual channel. With the help of institutionalization of such supportive behaviors, the issues of remote work can be alleviated, and the risks of turnover are decreased, along with an increase in employee satisfaction, engagement, and performance. Overall, the results prove that transformational leadership is a potent force of positive employee performance in the context of remote work, and perceived supervisor support is a critical process in the given context. By developing the theoretical ideas and presenting the practical facts, the research can be assessed as a contribution to the literature on leadership and organizational development that also provides the solution to the burning issue of how to approach employees in the fast-digitalizing world. Moreover, placing the analysis within the context of the IT sector in Pakistan, the investigation also expands the cross-cultural applicability of the leadership theory, showing that TL and supervisory support are still applicable in collectivist and emerging economy settings.

Limitations of the Study

Although it has contributed to it, the study has its limitations, which must be considered. To begin with, the cross-sectional design is limited to a causal interpretation; future research would be able to use longitudinal or experimental designs to document changes in leadership and employee outcomes over time. Two, the self-report surveys were used to collect the data, and this can be affected by common method bias, even with the protection

measures in place. Validity would be improved by the inclusion of multi-source data, including supervisor ratings or objective performance measures. Third, the research was done in the IT industry of Pakistan, which restricts the generalizability. Cross-industrial and cross-cultural comparative studies would contribute to the knowledge on how cultural norms and sectoral differences inform the influences of leadership and supervisory support. Such moderating variables as organizational culture, technological infrastructure, or team dynamics might also be examined in the future to gain a deeper understanding of remote work leadership.

Conclusion

This research infers that transformational leadership is a highly effective way of improving job satisfaction, work engagement, and performance among remote IT workers and that perceived supervisor support is a key mediating variable in these connections. These results generalize the leadership theory to the context of remote work and the importance of supervisory support as a psychological mechanism, and amplify knowledge in a collectivist, emerging economy context. In practice, the research highlights the necessity of having transformational leaders as well as supportive ones, as it is imperative that employees are motivated, engaged, and productive in online offices. With organizations still trying to adjust to the emerging world of remote and hybrid work, these leadership dynamics will be critical to the continuation of both individual and organizational well-being, and their exploitation will be vital.

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